

GLASS AND GLASS WARE EXPORT PERFORMANCE IN INDIA

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Cite This Article: Dr. N. Bhuvanesh Kumar & P. Sathrukana, "Glass and Glass Ware Export Performance in India", International Journal of Computational Research and Development, Volume 7, Issue 1, Page Number 63-65, 2022.

Abstract:

Exports have played an increasingly important role in India's economic growth in the last two decades. This paper analyses the performance of India's exports and the various economic factors which have contributed to its growth. Since manufactured exports comprise a significant share of India's aggregate (merchandise) exports, the paper also provides an overview study on the export performance of various products in glass and glassware.

Key Words: Glass and Glassware, Export Data, Commodity Analysis

Introduction:

Glass and Glassware is traded all around the world. The data provided on the export analysis shows that there are almost 99 countries and territories, which actively import Glass and Glassware from India. The combined value of total export is 82.3 USD million. Therefore, if any exporter wishes to export Glass and Glassware then Connect2India offers a complete guide on how to export Glass and Glassware from India. The following data contains everything from Glass and Glassware export analysis to export resources. The top five countries to export Glass and Glassware from India. From the perspective of the data on Glass and Glassware export, India's top 5 trade partners who import Glass and Glassware from Indian exporters are mentioned in the table, although the total export value of the top 5 countries is 79.56 USD million which is the 96.67% of the total export value of Glass and Glassware.

Statement of the Problem:

The glass industry faces a number of challenges continued price competition and growing labour shortages, lack of capacity and increasing pressure to innovate. The biggest challenges however is to reconcile all of this. However the solution is easy if you are open to fundamental challenges in the production process. With the conversion from a production line with individual processing stations to an integrated production line, this fundamental change can be implemented relatively easily. The further reduction of manual activities, progress in productivity and higher throughput, quality improvement and future security even in the age of Industry 4.0 – all this is part of such a solution and thus the answer to current and future challenges.

Objectives:

The research aims at enriching the knowledge understanding role of export performance of glass and glass ware. The following are the objective of the study.

- To study the country wise export performance of top major commodities.
- To provide necessary suggestion based on the findings of the study.

Scope of the Study:

The objective of this project is to cover the export performance of glass and glass ware from India. The export performance of India's glass and glass ware is affected by high competition. This study also gives growth rate and trend percentage of glass and glass ware for the year by year wise and also country wise. The study gives information about the glass and glass ware export. The study provides suggestions to improve their performance.

Research Methodology:

Secondary Data:

The secondary data is collected to supplement the primary data. The annual reports of sample units, Publications of Cotton products, in the website of Ministry of Commerce and Industries, Bulletins Working and Occasional Papers of EXIM Bank were used as important sources of secondary data for the study.

Limitations of the Study:

- The analysis is made only by considering glass and glass ware and 10 major countries.
- Time constraint is one of the limited.

Review of Literature:

J. M. L. Reis, J. L. V. Coelho, A. H. Monteiro, and H. S. Da Costa Mattos. The present work is concerned with the study of the damage behaviour of a composite material based on glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP). The main goal is to predict the rupture force using model equations that combine enough mathematical simplicity to allow their usage in engineering problems with the capability of describing a complex nonlinear mechanical behaviour.

K. Krushnamurty, D. Rasmitha, I. Srikanth, K. Ramji, C. Subrahmanyam, and A. R. Polymer Nano composites are currently one of the most rapidly growing families of materials, and they are finding use in a wide range of industrial applications, including aerospace and defense. The broad usage of composites is because of their consolidated mechanical properties. Glass fiber reinforced epoxy composites are available for the last few decades. The idea of adding nano clay into it has emerged in the late first decade of this century. This study is aimed at reporting the effects of the addition of nano clay into GFRP on its mechanical properties. L. F. P. Santos and B. Ribeiro, The purpose of this work is to evaluate the reconsolidation of a carbon fiber composite with poly (aryl ether ketone) (PAEK)/carbon fiber laminates after suffering impacts from different energy levels (5, 10 and 30 J) and being restored by reconsolidation. For this comparison, thermal analysis, and compression after impact tests were performed to evaluate the properties of the material before and after the reconsolidation process.

Exporting of Glass and Glassware from India:

Table 1

* Values in USD

Year	Australia	Growth Rate	Algeria	Growth Rate	Belgium	Growth Rate	Brazil	Growth Rate	Canada	Growth Rate
2009	7.47		0.4		14.26		14.33		2.59	
2010	7.03	-5.89	1.17	193	17.68	23.98	18.48	28.96	2.61	0.77
2011	8.67	23.33	0.64	-45	15.98	-9.62	25.94	40.37	4.2	60.92
2012	10.08	16.26	0.84	31	17.13	7.2	33.12	27.68	5.15	22.62
2013	10.49	4.07	0.77	-8	16.96	-0.99	29.93	-9.63	6.45	25.24
2014	10.7	2	0.64	-17	14.95	-11.85	24.28	-18.88	6.47	0.31
2015	7.5	-29.91	0.76	19	17.13	14.58	15.83	-34.8	6.3	-2.63
2016	8.62	14.93	1.04	37	14.27	-16.7	19.26	21.67	6.23	-1.11
2017	8.99	4.29	1.23	18	15.52	8.76	22.77	18.22	7.82	25.52
2018	8.23	-8.45	1.9	54	14.47	-6.77	22.43	-1.49	6.41	-18.03
2019	10.2	23.94	1.34	-29	17.07	17.97	26.47	18.01	4.91	-23.4
2020	11.82	15.88	1.61	20	13.28	-22.2	32.37	22.29	5.47	11.41
2021	13.33	12.77	2.21	37	26.54	99.85	29.91	-7.6	8.72	59.41
Total	123.13		14.55		215.24		315.12		73.33	
Average	9.47		1.12		16.56		24.24		5.64	

(Source In- Exim Data Bank-Ministry of Commerce)

Trend Analysis

2022	11.57		1.9		18.27		28.61		7.96	
2023	11.83		2		18.35		28.05		8.08	
2024	11.93		2.23		18.97		27.57		8.04	
2025	12.19		2.39		19.42		28		8.09	
2026	12.68		2.57		20.11		29.88		8.18	

Exporting of Glass and Glassware from India:

Table 2

* Values in USD

Year	Finland	Growth Rate	France	Growth Rate	Germany	Growth Rate	Indonesia	Growth Rate	Malaysia	Growth Rate
2009	1.66		8.55		10.55		6.21		1.41	
2010	0.95	-42.77	9.06	5.96	13.5	27.96	7.01	12.88	1.91	35.46
2011	0.62	-34.74	12.3	35.76	25.92	92	8.7	24.11	4.58	139.79
2012	0.21	-66.13	14.17	15.2	27.86	7.48	11.84	36.09	21.59	371.4
2013	0.38	80.95	14.44	1.91	36.21	29.97	11.15	-5.83	13.54	-37.29
2014	0.48	26.32	16.1	11.5	44.23	22.15	9.42	-15.52	15.68	15.81
2015	0.44	-8.33	14.63	-9.13	45.24	2.28	10.3	9.34	4.31	-72.51
2016	0.44	0	14.66	0.21	32.17	-28.89	7.23	-29.81	5.14	19.26
2017	0.28	-36.36	38.5	162.62	30.55	-5.04	5.15	-28.77	3.4	-33.85
2018	0.38	35.71	24.22	-37.09	42.64	39.57	6.24	21.17	18.94	457.06
2019	0.5	31.58	22.98	-5.12	33.98	-20.31	9.75	56.25	14.73	-22.23
2020	0.28	-44	23.12	0.61	35.39	4.15	7.69	-21.13	8.12	-44.87
2021	0.22	-21.43	32.79	41.83	43.92	24.1	13.12	70.61	3.9	-51.97
Total	6.84		245.52		422.16		113.81		117.25	
Average	0.53		18.89		32.47		8.75		9.02	

(Source in-Exim Data Bank-Ministry of Commerce)

Trend Analysis

2022	0.06		31.78		46.43		9.45		10.86	
2023	0.13		33.76		46.51		9.17		9.96	
2024	0.15		35.56		45.8		8.84		8.52	
2025	0.15		37.58		45.99		8.65		6.84	
2026	0.08		39.68		45.84		9		7.76	

Interpretation:

The Glass and glassware products export from India to Australia during the year of 2009 to 2021. It achieved highest value in the year of 2021 was USD 13.33. From growth rate analysis the Australia has achieved 9 years positive growth rate and remaining years are negative growth rate. While computing trend analysis to glass and glassware products for upcoming five years, it clearly shows export of glass and glassware products to the Australia will be increasing. Then India to Algeria growth rate 8 years are positive remaining years are negative growth rate. The trend analysis of Algeria upcoming 5 years are increasing. Next India to Belgium growth rate 6 years are positive and remaining years are negative growth rate. The trend analysis of Belgium upcoming 5 years are increasing. India to Brazil growth rate 7 years positive and remaining years are negative. The trend analysis of Brazil upcoming 5 years are increasing. And India to Canada growth rate 7 years are positive and remaining years are negative. The trend analysis of Canada upcoming 5 years is increasing. Then glass and glassware export performance from India to Finland growth rate are 5 years are positive and remaining years are negative. The trend analysis of Finland upcoming 5 years are fluctuation. India to France growth rate is 9 years are positive and remaining years are negative. The trend analysis of France upcoming 5 years is increasing. India to Germany growth rate is 9 years are positive and remaining years are negative. The trend analysis of Germany upcoming 5 years are fluctuation. India to Indonesia growth rate are 6 years are positive and remaining years are negative. The trend analysis of Indonesia upcoming 5 years is fluctuation. And India to Malaysia growth rate is 6 years are positive and remaining years are negative. The trend analysis of Malaysia upcoming 5 years is fluctuation.

Findings:

- The glass and glassware products export from India to Australia high growth rate value is 13.33. That year is 2021. India to Algeria high growth rate value is 2.21. That year is 2021. India to Belgium high growth rate value is 26.54. That year is 2021.
- India to Brazil high growth rate value is 33.12. That year is 2012. And India to Canada high growth rate value is 8.72. That year is 2021.
- Glass and glassware products exports from India to other countries are trend analysis of upcoming 5 years is highly increasing.
- The Glass and glassware export from India to Finland high growth rate value is 1.66. That year is 2009. India to France high growth rate value is 38.50. That year is 2017. India to Germany high growth rate value is 45.24. That year is 2015.
- India to Indonesia high growth rate value is 13.12. That year is 2021. And India to Malaysia high growth rate value is 21.59. That year is 2012.
- Glass and glassware exports from India to other countries are trend analysis of upcoming 5 years is highly increasing.

Suggestions:

- Export strategies should be based on an assessment of your own position and research into promising opportunities. So want to know about the export strategies.
- The government should pay more attention to export these products in large quantities.

Conclusion:

In this case the Glass and glass product export will study. To know about the India's Glass and glass production states and study about the exporting data. This study will using the methodology of secondary data, that data are collected in ministry of commerce and industries web page. Most of products will make a many negative growth rates, it will be makes a future analysis of decrease the growth but the demand will be a standard. So, these of above things are studied in this component

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